

IMPACT OF CHANGE IN DIETARY BEHAVIORS FOR INCREASE HB LEVEL OF ADOLESCENT GIRLS IN RURAL AREA

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Abstract

Adolescent is a transitional phase of growth and development between childhood and adulthood. Also this is a transitional stage of physical and psychological development. Adolescent health is the range of approaches to preventing, detecting or treating young people's health and well being. HB is the protein molecule in red blood cells that carries oxygen from the lungs to the body's tissues and return CO₂ from the tissues back to the lungs. HB also plays an important role in maintain the shape of the red blood cells. A low HB level is referred to as anemia. Some of the more common cause of anemia is nutritional deficiency. The problem is much more in rural area. For this study 20 rural Adolescent girls were selected as a subject. Age ranging 18-25 yrs. A study conducted in college. Subject change their dietary behavior regards to guideline for 60 days after that their HB was calculated. The study conclude that changing the dietary behavior, practice and increasing the awareness on rich food had positive impact and increased the HB levels of the rural Adolescent girls.

Keywords: HB, Adolescent Girls, Dietary Behaviors, Rural Area.

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Introduction

Adolescent is a transitional phase of growth and development between childhood and adulthood. Also this is a transitional stage of physical and psychological development that generally occurs during the period from puberty to legal adulthood. Adolescent health is the range of approaches to preventing, detecting or treating young people's health and well being. During this same physical changes affect the body's nutritional needs, while changes in one's lifestyle may affect eating habits and food choices adolescent nutritional is therefore important for supporting the physical growth of the body and for preventing future health problems. Any nutritional deficiency experienced during this critical period of life can have an effect on the future health of the individual. The study concludes that changing the dietary behavior, practice and increasing the awareness on rich food. Importance of eating dark green leafy vegetables, date, jiggery and peanuts, bit to maintain HB especially Adolescent girls. It was noted that intervention had positive impact and increased the HB levels of the rural Adolescent girls. HB is the protein molecule in red blood cells that carries oxygen from the lungs to the body's tissues and return co₂ from the tissues back to the lungs. HB also plays an important role in maintain the shape of the red blood cells. A low HB level is referred to as anemia. Some of the more common cause of anemia is nutritional deficiency. The problem is much more in rural area. Anemia was defined as the HB of less than 13.9 in male and 12.9 in female. Lack of access to balance diet or habits remain a major problem

related to HB. Lack of balanced diets, malnutrition is a major concern in rural area. This is affected health and well being as observed by the increased risk of anemia in adolescent girls. A low level of HB referred to as anemia, which leads to fatigue, confusion and weakness. So that take a balanced diet is very important for increase a level of HB. Adolescent nutrient is therefore important for supporting the physical growth of the body and for preventing future health problems.

Objectives

1. To find out the impact of change in dietary behaviors on HB levels in Adolescent girls.
2. Generate awareness regarding Balance diet in rural area.

Methodology

For this study 20 rural Adolescent girls were selected as a subject. Age ranging 18-25 yrs. A study conducted in college. Subject change their dietary behavior regards to guideline for 60 days after that their HB was calculated.

Result

Table No- 1 HB levels of Adolescent girl's pre and post intervention

HB Levels		Pre	Post
Serve	<8	4	2
Moderate	8- 10.9	11	5
Mild	11-11.9	3	5
Normal	>12	2	8

This table shows that 4 had serve, 11 Moderate, 3 Mild and 2 were normal HB level before intervention. After nutritional intervention the number of rural girls with normal range of hemoglobin was 8 thus the integration helped to increase HB level. The study concludes that changing the dietary behavior, practice and increasing the awareness on rich food. Importance of eating dark green leafy vegetables, date, jiggery and peanuts, bit to maintain HB especially Adolescent girls. It was noted that intervention had positive impact and increased the HB levels of the rural Adolescent girls.

Conclusion

Low HB level is a widespread deficiency in adolescent girls in rural area. Low HB level increase a health related problems. May limits their physical and mental growth. The present study shown that by increasing the awareness levels, knowledge and practice of eating balance diet and other food based strategies the HB levels of rural adolescent girls can be increased.

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